

Synthesis and *in vitro* Antibacterial Activity of Substituted Phenoxyacetic Acid Hydrazides

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A number of isatin derivatives are known to be physiologically active and some of them possess antibacterial^{1,2} and pesticidal properties³. Also hydrazones of isatin have been reported to act as potential antiviral⁴ and antibacterial agents⁵ apart from other potential biological activities^{6,7}. In view of these observations, we synthesised the hitherto unknown class of compounds *viz.* substituted phenoxyacetic acid (1-benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-3*H*-indol-3-ylidene) hydrazide and acetic/benzoic acid (1-benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-3*H*-indol-3-ylidene) (substituted phenoxyacetic acid) hydrazide and tested them for their antibacterial activity.

Substituted phenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (II), obtained by the reaction of substituted phenol with ethyl bromoacetate followed by treatment with hydrazine hydrate (99%)⁸, has been condensed with 1-benzoyl isatin, obtained from aniline, hydroxylamine and chloral hydrate⁹ followed by benzoylation¹⁰, to furnish substituted phenoxyacetic acid (1-benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-3*H*-indol-3-ylidene) hydrazide (IIIa-g). All these compounds have adequately been characterised by means of elemental analyses and the structures of these new compounds were in full agreement with their ir spectral data.

Treatment of IIIa-g with acetic anhydride/benzoylchloride in pyridine yielded acetic/benzoic acid (1-benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-3*H*-indol-3-ylidene) (substituted phenoxyacetic acid) hydrazide (IVa-n). Structures of these compounds were supported by their elemental analyses. Ir spectra showed bands at 1550 (C=N) and 1280, 1060cm⁻¹ (CH₂-O-Ar). Further, absence of bands in the region 3000 cm⁻¹ onwards confirmed the *N*-substitution of the acyclic -CO-NH- group.

Experimental

M.p.s were taken in open capillary tubes and were uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

Substituted phenoxyacetyl hydrazides (IIa-g) were prepared by the reported method⁸. Isatin was prepared⁹ from aniline, hydroxylamine and chloral hydrate and the corresponding 1-benzoylisatin (I) by the reported method¹⁰.

Phenoxyacetic acid (1-benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-3*H*-indol-3-ylidene)hydrazide (IIIa): A suspension of 1-benzoylisatin (I) (2.51 g, 0.01 mol) with AcOH (2 drops) in ethanol was refluxed, then IIa (1.66 g, 0.01 mol) was added to it after a few min and heating continued for about 6 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool and the solid mass thus obtained was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. Other hydrazones (IIb-g) were prepared in a similar manner and are listed in Table 1.

Acetic acid (1-benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-3*H*-indol-3-ylidene) (phenoxyacetic acid) hydrazide (IVa): To a solution of IIIa (3.99 g, 0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (50 ml) was added acetic anhydride (1.0 g, 0.01 mol). The resulting solution was heated on a steam bath for 4 h. A crystalline solid mass obtained was separated by filtration, washed with NaHCO₃ solution followed by ice cold water, and recrystallised from ethanol. Other such derivatives (IVb-n) were prepared in a similar manner (Table 1). While preparing IV(h-n), benzoyl chloride was taken in place of acetic anhydride.

Antibacterial activity: *In vitro* activity of compounds was carried out using the agar diffusion technique¹¹ against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus pumilus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. 5 mm diameter sterilized filter paper disc impregnated with 10 mg ml⁻¹ solution of the test compounds was placed on an agar plate seeded with the test organism. The seeded plates were incubated for 24 h at 37 ± 1° and the zone of inhibition of bacterial growth around the disc was then observed. Three replications of each test compound were made and tetracycline-HCl was used as control.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained showed that in the twenty one compounds the presence of *p*-bromo and

TABLE I - PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF HYDRAZONES (IIIa-g AND IVa-n)

Compd. no.	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %	N% ; Found/ (Calcd.)
R - H				
IIIa	H	221	70	10.61 (10.52)
IIIb	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	228	80	10.18 (10.16)
IIIc	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	236	76	10.23 (10.16)
IIId	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	241	90	10.21 (10.16)
IIIe	<i>p</i> -Cl	248	85	9.61 (9.69)
IIIf	<i>p</i> -Br	226	60	8.95 (8.78)
IIIg	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	237	65	13.44 (12.61)
R - CH₃				
IVa	H	185	60	9.65 (9.52)
IVb	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	176	55	9.12 (9.23)
IVc	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	155	50	9.21 (9.23)
IVd	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	165	65	9.26 (9.23)
IVe	<i>p</i> -Cl	178	63	8.65 (8.83)
IVf	<i>p</i> -Br	164	54	8.11 (8.07)
IVg	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	195	62	11.56 (11.52)
R - C₆H₅				
IVh	H	208	72	8.12 (8.34)
IVi	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	192	65	8.24 (8.12)
IVj	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	181	70	8.15 (8.12)
IVk	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	201	66	8.17 (8.12)
IVl	<i>p</i> -Cl	208	75	7.45 (7.81)
IVm	<i>p</i> -Br	188	70	7.15 (7.21)
IVn	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	210	65	10.12 (10.21)

Satisfactory C and H analysis was obtained.

p-nitro groups in the phenoxy ring [compds. no. III(f,g) and IV(f,g,m,n)] exhibited more pronounced antibacterial activity than rest of the compounds tested. It was further noticed that the introduction of acetyl or benzoyl substituted on acyclic -CO-NH- group effects a decrease in the antibacterial activity. This decrease in the activity is maximum when the benzoyl group is substituted on -CO-NH- (comps. no. IVm, n). Against *S. aureus*, all these six compounds exhibited increased activity, whereas against *B. subtilis* and *B. pumilus*, comparatively lesser antibacterial activity was observed, except compd. no. IVg which showed pronounced antibacterial activity against *B. pumilus*.

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Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of Aryloxyacetyl Hydrazones of Fluoro Aralkyl/Diaryl Ketones

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KHAN and Bahel¹ prepared fluorinated aryl hydrazones as fungicides. The -CONH-N=C= moiety of hydrazones imparts biological activities to such compounds². Various hydrazones have been reported useful as fungicides^{3,4}, bactericides⁵ and psychotropics⁶. In view of these observations, we have prepared the title hydrazones which might display significant activity due to presence of fluorine and an aryloxyacetyl moiety.

The hydrazones (III) have been obtained by the condensation of aryloxyacetyl hydrazines (I) and fluorinated aralkyl/diaryl ketones (II) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

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